

Impact of COVID-19 On The Performance of Business Operations of Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Covid-19 awareness, Performance, Mediator, SOPs.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5527168</p>	<p><i>Covid-19 has affected everyone around the world in one way or the other. Despite of getting vaccinated against Corona virus and following SOPs recommended by the WHO, the number of people affected by the virus has been increasing at a rising rate. In Pakistan all the business sectors have faced downfall and are performing less. Pharmaceutical industry is one of the business operations which got affected from this pandemic. This study is an attempt to find the impact of awareness of COVID-19 on the performance of pharmaceutical firms of KPK. Moreover the mediating effect of standard operating procedures on the relationship between COVID-19 and business performance has also been analyzed. Data was collected from 131 firms using self-administered questionnaire. The results found that SOPs (Standard Operating Procedure) recommended by the WHO mediates the relationship of Covid-19 awareness and the firm's performance. Policy makers at all levels should pay more attention to the impact of COVID-19 on pharmaceutical firms and adopt strategies to reduce the damage.</i></p>

Introduction

The entire world is making an effort to deal with an infectious disease COVID-19 caused by a newly discovered corona virus which was originated from Wuhan, China. This pandemic has not only affected more than 215 countries of the world with deaths of 3954324 and confirmed cases of 182319261 (World Health organization) but also disturbed the economic, social, political, religious and financial structures of the whole world. The pandemic has hit really hard to the world and brought health related hardships. Nearly all the affected countries have implemented local and national lockdowns leading to closure of educational institutes and all the businesses, wide scale social distancing and banning of mass gatherings and public events. Due to Covid-19, the world is experiencing a difficult economic situation since World War II. In the face of this pandemic where countries like World's topmost economies such as the UK, US, Japan, Italy, France, China, US, Germany and many others are at the verge of collapse it has also affected the developing countries to a greater extent. In Pakistan, the Covid-19 has also spread its roots very deeply.

The first case of COVID-19 was reported in Karachi on 26th Feb, 2020 when a student tested positive after returning from Iran. The virus got spread very quickly in all the provinces of Pakistan by March 18 which is a very short span of time as a result of which nationwide lockdown was put on 1st April, 2020. The lock down affected several businesses like travelling, enterprises, tourism, sports, entertainment, transport etc. which affected the economy very badly. According to the Pakistan's government, the corona virus epidemic cost the country Rs2.5 trillion on April 2nd. The shutdown measures have already impacted small businesses and SMEs to a large extent. Due to increased unemployment, the Pakistan's Government gave permission to open a few of the businesses provided that Standard Operating Procedures are followed properly. In the face of this pandemic which affected all the provinces of Pakistan, KPK (Khyber Pakhtunkhwa) was among the highest where most deaths were reported because of COVID-19. In KPK, the low risk businesses which were allowed to resume activities included hairdresser shops, electrical market, chicken and egg shops, auto spare parts, paper & packaging, stationery shops and pharmaceuticals have been allowed to remain open from 9am to 5pm. These businesses have been working by following the SOPs recommended by World Health Organization (WHO) which includes maintaining social distancing, regular hand washing, surface cleaning and wearing face masks. The purpose of this study is to analyse the impact of COVID-19 on the performance of the businesses of KPK keeping in view the SOPs recommended by WHO.

Research Objectives:

The following are the objectives this study intends to achieve are:

1. To analyze the impact of awareness of COVID-19 on the performance of pharmaceutical firms of KPK.

2. To analyze the mediating effect of standard operating procedures on the relationship between COVID-19 and business performance.

Literature Review

The world has changed dramatically in just a few months. Thousands have died and millions have become ill as a result of a coronavirus that was previously unknown until it appeared in the Chinese city of Wuhan in December 2019. Millions of people have been affected by the disease, and their entire life style has changed as a result. Coronavirus disease 2019 (abbreviated as “COVID- 19”) is a disease of respiratory tract due to a new corona virus which was first detected in 2019 in the month of December. Myalgia, dry cough, fever, tiredness and dyspnea are the primary clinical signs of the illness, which is extremely contagious. Sudden severe respiratory distress syndrome, renal failure, pneumonia and possibly death are possible complications (Lai et al., 2020; Lake, 2020). COVID-19 was declared a global public health emergency by the World Health Organization on January 30, 2020, due to the disease's fast spread, which was already seen in December 2019 and January 2020(Wang, F. S., & Zhang, 2020). The coronavirus that causes this disease, known as SARS-CoV-2, is most likely to have a zoonotic origin. The scarcity of resources, which has turned this issue into a worldwide healthcare and social emergency, necessitates a concerted effort from everyone and all organizations concerned. [Rabi et al., 2020; WHO, 2020].It should also not be forgotten that the search for an effective therapy, which is yet unavailable, necessitates unprecedented collaboration between healthcare practitioners and the scientific community (Rodríguez et al., 2020).

As for as the impact of Covid-19 is concerned, it effects every angle of life.Covid-19, a pandemic, has infected the whole planet, causing Enchlophobia. The reason is that although the vaccine has been discovered and people around the world are getting vaccinated but still the virus is changing its shape so there is a chaos that vaccine is not effective for variants. We are left with no other preventive option other than observing social distance in order to break the viral transmission chain.In the current circumstance, streets all across the world are desolate after authorities imposed a severe lockdown due to Covid-19.Since World War II, Italy has imposed the most extensive travel restrictions. The usually busy theatres, bars and pubs in London have been shuttered, and residents have been advised to remain at home. Worldwide flights are being turning around or cancelled because of the buckling of the aviation industry. It's all in the sake of slowing the spread of Covid-19 and, ideally, lowering the mortality toll. However, all of this upheaval has resulted in some unexpected consequences. Industries, transportation networks, and companies have all shut down as a result.

As for as the pharmaceutical industry is concerned, it is playing a vital role in eradicating Covid-19 by following SOPs. Because of SOPs their operations and supply of finished goods from the place of production to the place of consumption is badly suffered.As far the outbreak of coronavirus in Pakistan is concerned, this is a difficult time since the epidemic has slowed global economic activity, and Pakistan's pharmaceutical sector has been hit hard. Due to a shutdown in numerous foreign nations, Pakistan's pharmaceutical sector has expressed concern over a lack of imported raw materials needed for various medications to tackle the threat of coronavirus.The Pakistan Pharmaceutical Manufacturers' Association (PPMA) has about 770 registered medicine firms that employ 1,200 molecules and other active pharmaceutical components for making 98,000 medicinal goods. The country imports 95% of its raw material from Beijing and Shanghai while the rest comes from Italy, Japan and Spain. After the complete lifting of lock down by the government of Pakistan, the pharma industry is expected to carry out its production while following SOPs recommended by the WHO.

Awareness related to COVID-19

More than half a million people around 200 countries are infected by COVID-19 despite of taking strict measures implemented by the governments like lock downs. The virus is spreading with a fast pace. In such a situation where the policy makers are giving due consideration to protect the people from getting affected from this virus, creating awarness among people about COVID-19 is an uphill task. Awareness level plays a pivotal role in timely and effective prevention of novel corona (Hussain, Khan, Gilani&Raza, 2020) and because of person to person interaction and high level of exposure to the environment, awareness and dealing regarding with this virus is very crucial. Like many other countries, Pakistan is also facing the unique challenge of creating awareness in the people regarding how this virus spreads, symptoms related to it, how to prevent from getting infected and how to win battle agaisnt this virus. In this regard, the National Action Plan for COVID–19 has been initiated by the Government of Pakistan where media compagin regarding generating awareness among people has been initiated which focuses on the cotrol of the infection by following measures recommended by the WHO. In this backdrop, where a lock down is partially lifted and the businesses become more vulnerable to COVID-19, creating awareness and dealing regarding with this virus is very crucial. People are becoming aware of the Covid-19 and the consequences of avoiding protective measures against this virus. In Pakistan, the pharmaceutical firms are making sure to use this awareness in a constructive way and change the life style of their business operations by following the SOPs recommended by the WHO. In the light of the above discussion, we hypothesize the following:

H1: Awareness of Covid-19 has a significant impact on the SOPs in the pharmaceutical firms.

SOPs by the WHO

The WHO has in its new Global Humanitarian Response Plan (nGHRP) has advised an action plan regarding how to deal with this pandemic. Most of the countries including Pakistan are following this action plan to combat against this novel virus. According to WHO, ways to reduce COVID-19 are as follows:

1. Social distancing:

A social distance of 6 feet/ 2 meter is required to be maintained from one another. It implies to maintain a deliberately physical space between two persons to avoid spreading the virus.

2. Hand Washing:

Frequently washing of hands for at least 20 seconds with soap and water is to be done. In case of unavailability of soap and water, use of hand sanitizer (at least 60% of alcohol) is to be ensured.

3. Surface Cleaning:

Frequently touched objects and surfaces are disinfected and cleaned frequently by wearing gloves. Discard the gloves and immediate washing of the hands after cleaning the surface.

4. Face masks and PPE:

Use of N95 mask or a 3 folded cloth which covers chin, mouth and nose whereas for health worker, use of PPE is to be ensured.

5. Self-isolation:

In case of exposure to COVID-19, a self-isolation of minimum 14 days is to be done.

Methodology of the Study

The current research work is basically aim to investigate the effect of Covid-19 on life style as mediator and performance as dependent variable. The current study is unique in nature because the study have not done before and the antecedent were not explored before in Pakistan.

Research Instruments

Self-administered questionnaire was made and used for data collection. Questionnaire was mainly based on measurement of the dependent, mediator and independent variables. In current research work variable were measured on the basis of 5 point Likertscale which are considered a common scale of measurement in social sciences.

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire used for the study consist of cover letter, profile of the respondents, antecedents for performance of pharmaceuticals firms by using SOPs and the closing part of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was started from cover letter which explain the purpose and importance of the research and the survey. According to Dillman (2000) explaining the purpose of research to respondents increase their interest in survey. The current questionnaire was consist of three parts. Part 1 (demographic factor), part 2 (antecedents) and part 3 contain items of (performance).

Targeted Population and Sample Size

Targeted population for the existing study was pharmaceutical firms residing in Pakistan. But keeping the current situation in front it was difficult to collect the data from all over country. The researcher select pharmaceuticals firms in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa as sample size. These respondents were selected on the basis of convenient sampling. 131 Respondents were selected from given 1200 population of pharmaceuticals firms by using (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970) formula to determine the sample size.

Formula for Determining Needed Sample Size

POPULATION SIZE UNKNOWN:

$$\text{SAMPLE SIZE} = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{RANGE}}{2}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{\text{ACCURACY LEVEL}}{\text{CONFIDENCE LEVEL}}\right)^2}$$

Confidence Levels:

	α	$\alpha/2$
.10 level =	1.28	1.64
.05 level =	1.64	1.96
.01 level =	2.33	2.58
.001 level =	3.09	3.29

Accuracy Levels:

Range X	Desired Level of Accuracy (expressed as a proportion)
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POPULATION SIZE KNOWN:

$$\text{SIZE} = \frac{X^2 NP (1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + X^2 P (1-P)}$$

X^2 = table value of Chi-Square @ *d.f.* = 1 for desired confidence level

.10 = 2.71 .05 = 3.84 .01 = 6.64 .001 = 10.83

N = population size

P = population proportion (assumed to be .50)

d = degree of accuracy (expressed as a proportion)

Data Collation Method

For the current research study both primary and secondary methods were used for data collection. The primary data was collected through the survey process which is needed for the purpose to test the hypotheses. On the other hand, secondary data were collected from journals and many other sources to develop the hypothesis in order to support the research study.

Analysis and Result

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of the Respondents

	Characteristics	Frequency	Percent%
Gender	Male	98	75%
	Female	33	25%
	Total	131	100%
Age	20 to 25	15	11.4%
	26 to 30	60	45.8%
	31 to 35	25	19%
	36 to 40	15	11.4%
	Above 40	16	12.2%
	Total	131	100%
Education	Master	93	71%
	MS/M.Phil	32	24.4%
	Ph.D	06	5%
	Total	131	100%
Experience	1 to 4 years	100	76.3%
	5 to 7 years	15	11.5%
	8 to 11 years	10	8%
	Above 11 years	06	5%
	Total	131	100%

Table 1 illustrates the results taken from the dissemination of the respondents selected in the existing study on the basis of education, age, gender and experience. It is suggested that male respondents were in majority for the purpose of data collection. Male respondents were 98 with 75% and female were 33 with 25%

of the total sample size. On the basis of age from the total sample size 26 to 30 years of age respondents were in majority following by 31 to 35 and so on. The table further indicates that majority of the respondents had Master's degree as qualification. They were 71% of the total respondent following by M.Phil and Ph.D. According to the table above, those with 1 to 4 years of experience were in the majority, followed by 5 to 7 years, and so on.

Reliability Statistics

Table 2: Overall Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	No of Variables
.851	3

Table 2 indicates reliability statistics used in the current study. The overall reliability of questionnaire and constructs is .851 which mean that the data set is reliable for further analysis. .85 is more than the cutoff value of .70.

Table 3: Reliability Statistics

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Performance of Pharmaceuticals firms	.810
SOPs by WHO	.791
Awareness of Covid-19	.839

The findings of the Table 3 shows that the values of each variable cross the acceptable range of Cronbach's alpha. The value of each variable is more than .70 which is well above the acceptable range.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 4: Reliability Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Performance of Pharmaceuticals firms	131	3.11	4.67	3.8519	.25605
SOPs by WHO	131	3.20	4.60	3.8341	.42208
Awareness of Covid-19	131	3.40	4.60	3.8955	.28761

The descriptive statistics employed in this study were used to determine the characteristics of the data compiled from the chosen sample. The effects exhibited that the performance of pharmaceuticals firms (*PPFI*) is having lowest value of 3.11 with maximum value of 4.67, mean value is 3.85 and standard deviation is .256. SOPs by WHO (*SOPWHO*) construct having smallest value of 3.20 with highest value of 4.60, mean of the construct is 3.834 and .42208 is the standard deviation. Awareness of Covid-19 (*AC-19*) construct has a minimum value of 3.40 and 4.60 a maximum value. Furthermore, it has a mean value of 3.895 and .28761 is the standard deviation.

Assumptions' Statistics for Factor Analysis

Table 5: Factor Analysis

Constructs	DCM	KMO	BTS	Sig
Performance of Pharmaceuticals Firms	.001	.798	1799.894	000*
SOPs by WHO	.314	.740	301.601	000*
Awareness of Covid-19	.028	.825	789.459	000*

DCM: Determinant of Correlation Matrix

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy

Bartlette's Test of Sphericity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin(KMO) is a way for testing the sample adequacy. According to Huck (2012), data set is considered acceptable when the value of KMO is not less than $<.60$ which means that it should be greater than .60. Of the value is less than .60, it indicates that data is not up to par (Pallant, 2011). KMO measures of the present study is given in Table 5. After KMO, determinant of Correlation matrix comes where correlation between inter-variables are conducted. According to Pallant (2011), the value of correlation should be equal to .3 or greater. Field (2005) suggested that the determinant of the Correlation matrix be larger than .0000. For this purpose, Bartlett's of sphericity has been used. Table 5 presents the values of DCM and Bartlette's Test of Sphericity are in the acceptable range.

1. Relationship between Awareness of COVID-19 and Performance

Table 6 indicates the results of association between Awareness of Covid-19 and Performance of Pharmaceutical firms. The regression analysis reveals that Awareness of Covid-19 has a significant impact on the performance as $p < 0.001$ at 0.1% where $F=19.9333$ and $p=.000$. Table 4 further reveals that 13.4% variations in the Performance is explained by Awareness of Covid-19. The results lead to the acceptance of H2.

Table 6: Awareness of Covid-19 and Performance

	Beta coefficients	t-value	Sig
Constant	1.374	5.955	.000
Awareness of COVID-19	.246	4.465	.000

Notes: $R^2 = .134$; $F=19.9333$; $Sig = .000$

Dependent Variable: Performance

2. Relationship between Awareness of COVID-19 and SOPs

Table 7 indicates the results of association between Awareness of Covid-19 and SOPs of Pharmaceutical firms. The regression analysis reveals that Awareness of Covid-19 has a significant impact on the performance as $p < 0.001$ at 0.1% where $F=10.846$ and $p=.001$. Table 5 further reveals that 7.8% variations in the SOPs are explained by Awareness of Covid-19. The results lead to the acceptance of H1.

Table 7: Awareness of Covid-19 and SOPs

	Beta coefficients	t-value	Sig
Constant	2.383	5.854	.000
Awareness of COVID-19	.320	3.293	.001

Notes: $R^2 = .078$; $F=10.846$; $Sig = .001$

Dependent Variable: SOPs

3. Mediating Effect of SOPs

Table 8 presents the mediating impact of SOPs on the relationship between Awareness of Covid-19 and Performance of Pharmaceutical firms according to Baron & Kenny's method of mediation (1986). According to this method, a variable acts as a mediator when it meets the following requirements:

1. When IV predicts the dependent variable.
2. When IV predicts the presumed mediator.
3. When IV and mediator predict the dependent variable.

The above mentioned requirement no 1 and 2 have been fulfilled in Table 4 and 5. Table 6 presents two models. Model 2 represents the direct impact of SOPs on the performance leading to the acceptance of H3 as $p < 0.001$. SOPs act a mediator since it mediates the association between Awareness of Covid-19 and Performance. The results reveal that R^2 (coefficient of determination) is increased and the beta coefficients have decreased from Model 1 to Model 2 for the variable Awareness of Covid-19 which explains the role of SOPs as a mediator.

Table 8: SOPs as a mediator

	Model 1 Regression without SOPs B (p-values)	Model 2 Regression with SOPs B (p-values)
Awareness of COVID-19	.246(.000)	.224(.000)
SOPs	- $R^2 = .134$.070 (.161) $R^2 = .147$
	R^2 change= .134; F change=19.933; Sig F. change =.000	R^2 change= .013; F change=11.038; Sig F. change=.000

Discussion

Where a number of studies found the impact of Covid-19 on firm's performance is negative (Aifuwa, Saidu&Aifuwa, 2020; Fu and Shen 2020; Gil-Alana and Monge 2020; Shen, Fu, Pan, Yu, & Chen, 2020;) this study found that it is not negative when management has awareness of Covid-19 and it ensures to adopt and follow the SOPs recommended by the WHO. The results of the study give surprising results to the existing body

of knowledge that where prior studies and considering the novel Covid-19 outbreak as a matter of serious concerns for the firms around the world, this study has found that still the performance of firms can be enhanced and smooth running of the firms is possible when proper knowledge related to the novel virus is acquired by the management. Furthermore the performance can be further enhanced if SOPs are to be followed while doing day to day operations in the firms. Hence SOPs act as a mediator between the relationship of awareness of Covid-19 and firm's performance. The pharmaceutical firms are working day and night and putting in their efforts to render their services even in this critical situation where stepping out of home is a serious concern, performing well is more than a blessing which is achieved by following the SOPs recommended by the World Health Organization.

Implications

The findings of this study are going to be useful for the CEOs and top management of all the business operations generally and pharmaceutical firms of KPK particularly as it focuses on how the awareness related to Covid-19 can enhance their performance. Furthermore the policy makers can initiate effective awareness programs and devise effective strategies regarding following SOPs recommended by WHO in order to ensure safe Pakistan. The findings of the study are important in theory as it builds up the gap in the existing body of knowledge by proposing a model which unique set of variables which focuses on how to improve the performance of all the businesses by implementing and following the basic guide lines recommended by the WHO.

Conclusion

Awareness of Covid-19 can play a pivotal role in leading any business's performance to success. In such a situation where almost every business is affected by Covid-19 in Pakistan, performance of businesses can be enhanced by adopting SOPs recommended by the WHO. In a socio-cultural environment of Pakistan, where giving awareness to the people to adopt SOPs is like an uphill task, still the policy makers have made it possible that people follow the SOPs in order to perform well and increase their businesses' performance. Awareness of Covid-19 is crucial not only for the CEOs (upper management) and managers (middle management), but also to the employees involved in day to day operations so as to make sure the smooth running of the organization in the uncertain environment of this pandemic.

Future Direction

This study is focused on KPK only hence future studies may generalize the results by investigating the variables of interest on all the provinces of Pakistan. The present study is limited to only pharmaceutical industry of KPK. Future research is needed to analyze the relationship of variables under study on other industries of Pakistan which are working hard in this pandemic hence it will give insight into the clear picture of how industries of Pakistan are coping with Covid-19. In addition to this, there might be variables who act as moderators in the relationship between Awareness of Covid-19 and performance of Pharmas which has not been checked by this study. In future scholars are needed to check the role of moderators on the variables.

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